

The Composites Affordability Initiative (CAI)

The Benefits of Getting the US Government & Airframe Producers to Cooperate

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Background

The Composites Affordability Initiative (CAI) is a cooperative effort between government and industry to reduce the cost of aerospace composite structures, allowing design engineers to take full advantage of their unique benefits. The program launched in 1996 and is scheduled to run through 2017. CAI member companies include Lockheed Martin at Fort Worth, Texas; Northrop Grumman at El Segundo, California; Boeing Phantom Works at St. Louis, Missouri and Seattle, Washington; General Electric Aircraft Engine Division in Cincinnati, Ohio; the U.S. Air Force Materials Lab at Wright Patterson AFB in Dayton, Ohio; and the U.S. Naval Air Warfare Center in Patuxent River, Maryland.

The Challenge: Making Smart Decisions Early

A major obstacle identified by the group was that designers, early in the concept stage when most important decisions are made, had no way to determine the impact of their choices on program cost. The hitch is that composite manufacturing is both more complex than traditional metal working processes, and at the same time less familiar to today's designers. As a result, designers working on new concepts have no way to determine the cost impact of the critical decisions they're making. The traditional method of costing a design involves the submission of the concept to an analyst to conduct a cost study, a process that typically takes about two weeks. The biggest setback with this approach is that a considerable amount of additional time and money will have already been invested into the design by the time the study is complete. Another obstacle introduced by this method is that the design has typically changed significantly in those two weeks, meaning the original cost study will have become obsolete.

The Goal: Accurate Cost Estimates in “Real-Time”

The managers of the CAI wanted to develop a software tool capable of providing accurate cost estimates in “real time,” essentially a compass that would point to the lowest cost alternative at every step of the design process.

The CAI is based on the idea that the key to significant cost reductions in composite aerospace structures is to further develop “composites friendly” designs, simulation tools and material and manufacturing processes. Tools and technology necessary to provide integrated product teams with improved methods for designing composite airframes are being developed under the program. The final goal will be to develop revolutionary design techniques, innovative manufacturing concepts, materials, and processes, advanced simulation and modeling tools, and advanced business practices to enable breakthrough reductions in cost, schedule, and weight. The initial focus has been on manned fixed wing strike fighter aircraft structural applications, but the technologies validated will be applicable to all classes of aerospace structures from ground vehicles to spacecraft.

Composites Affordability Initiative Cost Analysis Tool (CAICAT)

The first step in moving toward the goals identified was the formation of the CAI Cost Team. Once the team was established they began documenting the cost model requirements, both from a user perspective and from the software development view. The logistics of whom and how the model should operate were identified.

During this process, all CAI cost team member companies brought forth model candidates for review by the team. Prior to the formation of the CAI, a team of Boeing Company Phantom Works engineers, including Falque, was assigned to produce and validate a proof-of-concept Boeing proprietary cost tool. Boeing’s concept was brought to the CAI cost team, reviewed, and accepted it as one of the CAI’s costing concepts.

The next step was to search for an off-the-shelf, commercially available solution. No solution was identified, so the cost team put out a CBD announcement. The responding companies were invited to participate in technical interchange meetings with the team, where their proposed solutions were evaluated in comparison with the CAI’s requirements.

The CAICAT Solution: SEER-DFM™

The packages examined by the team fell into three categories. One category consisted of high-level parametric tools that provided basic guidelines, such as dollars per pound of finished part. The second operated at the process level and used metrics such as x inches of material can be laid up per minute. The third was a very detailed model based on work measurement standards, such as x minutes to set up the blade, y minutes to advance the cutter, etc. CAI cost team engineers decided that the process-based approach was the most practical because it offered the best mix of accuracy and speed.

The CAI cost team decided to base their development efforts on the SEER-DFM™ software package from Galorath Incorporated (www.galorath.com) because it provides a powerful framework for estimation and analysis while offering a unique capability of accepting custom cost models as plug-ins. Another reason for selecting SEER-DFM for customization was that the off-the-shelf version of the tool already had powerful composite manufacturing cost estimation capabilities in addition to traditional metal working processes such as machining, sheet metal fabrication and assembly. This facilitates quick tradeoffs between traditional metal working processes and newer advanced composite processes.

Fostering Collaboration

The key to success was in the sharing of cost data between competing contractors. The cost team decided on a level of data that made it possible for the contractors to share information, without compromising their competitive advantages. SEER-DFM allowed for the application of time standards at the process level, a factor that tremendously helped foster collaboration. Each of the member companies had developed their own standards to forecast costs in the production of their parts and assemblies. The CAI cost team realized that at the raw standards level, the costing data was not proprietary. It did however become proprietary to each company when labor calibrations, variances to standards, improvement curves and the labor rates were taken into account.

Having realized this through the use of SEER-DFM, companies now have the ability to work together and share data on all types of projects. In order to share data in a teaming or competitive environment, the companies must agree to labor calibrations, variances to standards, improvement curves and labor rates.

When the parameters and values have been established, it becomes possible for companies to transmit costing data between team members and the customer, in the development of engineering design studies or program. Once the design studies are complete and the proposal phase initiated, each company works individually to formulate their proposal before submitting them to the customer. The data in each proposal is proprietary, and only to be shared with the customer.

Customizing the Model

To validate the concept, the CAI cost team contracted Galorath to develop a simple model of a proprietary composite process. Next, they demonstrated the model to engineers from each CAI member company.

Upon concept evaluation and approval, teams of engineers from each member company began working together to develop the custom process models to evaluate the cost of the latest composite manufacturing techniques. Under the influence of the government managers of the program, all team members agreed to share both the process models and the details of the processes themselves, an unprecedented step in an industry known for its secrecy.

An example of the technology being modeled includes Boeing's new composite manufacturing process, based on stitched resin film infusion (RFI) that prevents de-lamination, allowing fabrication of full-span composite wings. Stitched RFI technology is expected to reduce wing weight by 25% and cost by 20% within 3 years.

Each of the engineering teams created models defining the costs of their manufacturing processes. The models, in the form of spreadsheets mostly, were supplied to a Galorath team. As each model was completed, Galorath's team encapsulated it in a plug-in, taking advantage of the SEER-DFM architecture that provides the framework to easily integrate custom models. Each plug-in is built as a separate executable, in the form of direct library link (DLL) that carries a database with process information.

The use of a discrete database containing all values used to define the cost of the process, such as dollars per pound for various materials or minutes per square inch, makes it easy to update the model to account for price changes or process improvements. This makes it possible for engineers from the different companies involved in the project to easily accommodate their own company's internal standards.

The SEER-DFM with composites plug-in currently has about 25 process models and another 25 in the development pipeline. CAI cost team member engineers have tested the early models and given them glowing reviews.

Standard SEER-DFM has the following processes:

- Fabrication
- Casting & Forging
- Machining
- Assembly
- PC Board Assembly
- Heat Treatment & Finishing
- Composites
- Electrical Assembly
- Additional Items
- Purchased Parts

The CAI Cost Team determined that the assembly and composites modules would need to be enhanced to reflect the processes emerging in aerospace manufacturing. As a result, industry wide data was collected to enable Galorath to add the following “CAI plug-ins” to SEER-DFM:

Material Placement	Assembly & Fabrication	Cure & Infusion
Hand Lay-up	Fit Up	Autoclave
Braiding	Drill	RTM
Tow Placement	Fasten	VARTM
P4A	Trim	E-Beam
3D Weaving	Paste Bond	Insitu-E-Beam
Filament Winding	E-Beam Assembly	
	3-D Reinforcement	
	Automated Assembly	
	Fabrication	

Sheet Metal
SPF/DB
Chemical Milling
High Speed Machining
Core Machining

An Integrated Solution

The long-term goal is to integrate the cost estimation model with the CAD packages used by CAI team members, primarily CATIA and Unigraphics. This will make it possible for the engineer to work at a CAD station, create a model and SEER-DFM will automatically provide the cost. In the overall CAI scheme, SEER-DFM is viewed as the cost engine for a constellation of models that will tie the cost communities of the various companies together. The final goal is to build a total life cycle model that will incorporate all of the expenses involved in building, operating, maintaining and disposing of a particular composite structure. The SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in is an interactive tool designed for use by product development teams to rapidly assess the acquisition and life cycle costs of structural components throughout the design and manufacturing process. The tool is designed primarily for trade study use; however, estimators to provide specific estimates for components can easily use it. Trades can be done on elements of process i.e. selecting one cutter type versus another and trading one process versus another, such as Tow Placement versus Hand Lay-up. The modeled processes include state of practice, state of the art and emerging technologies, with special attention focused on fabricated composite processes and components. SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in is a compilation of many fabrication processes, called process modules. These process modules can be used individually or collectively to estimate the cost of specific designs or fabrication solutions, and calculates the weight of a design as defined. Immediate availability of these estimates allows designers to trade cost factors on equal terms with schedule, performance and weight factors.

With cost factors being treated as design requirements, a method was required to rapidly trade cost with weight and other performance goals. In addition, the development of new fabrication processes required a method that can be used to equally trade one process with another for a particular component design. SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in is designed to allow user evaluation of alternative design, manufacturing,

and cost factors, thus achieving optimal solutions. Team-generated inputs for each module will provide optimum estimates; however, the model can be used by persons operating independently. When designers want to do independent trade studies on various designs there is a recommended approach that is available using SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in. Preliminary work needed to be done first, by developing templates of all the SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in modules. The templates are preset for all of the program parameters (i.e. production qty, wrap rate \$, lot qty, etc.), process related work steps (i.e. debulking interval set at every 5 plies), and equipment settings (i.e. ply cutting set to the water jet cutter). In this approach the Knowledge Base Templates may be used to model your production shop's equipment, functionality, and project/production requirements. All the design staff has to do is select the desired process module and enter design requirements such as size (i.e. length, width, area and thickness etc.), material type (i.e. graphite, titanium or aluminum etc.), to produce trade study results.

Each SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in module work element represents a process or series of process steps that can be selected. A process is the method used to manufacture a detail part or the method used to assemble detail parts into assemblies. They are made up of process steps or elements that are the major cost drivers for any given process. Process steps are sometimes broken down into sub-steps or sub-elements to provide visibility to the discreet cost drivers within a process. The SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in is comprised of modules (work elements) that describe the detailed steps of selected fabrication processes. Each of these modules contains elements that describe a particular process used to fabricate a structural component using capabilities currently available in a typical factory setting. Each process module and its verified data set are summarized in each work element.

Users can tailor the SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in to fit the component being estimated. Each process module provides the basic operations needed to fabricate a component. The basic concept is that SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in is a process-based model, not a part-specific model. However, parts can easily be estimated by linking processes together. Major assemblies and total vehicle structures can also be modeled. For example, if you have a simple hand laid up spar you would insert a roll up work element and then insert a hand lay-up module, a cure module and a trim module to attain the part total answer. This breaks away from the traditional part models giving SEER-DFM with the CAI Plug-in the added flexibility of being a model that is made up of building blocks. The user can stack or re-stack as required for any

given project, program, or basic trade study and thus make it a constant, reusable resource instead of the typical part model that you have to re-build each time a new project begins.

The model has many built-in features. For example, one accommodates risk assessments throughout the analysis, by way of SEER-DFM's allowance for least, likely and most inputs. The user may also take advantage of built-in risk analysis features by using these input ranges. If the ranges are not used, a single point estimate is still provided. These ranges are used to formulate the Monte Carlo risk analysis, another feature built into the model. This provides a powerful way of reducing risk and capturing any uncertainty in the components being modeled. The model allows management, for the first time, to view the correlation of cost with the extremes of success and failure of the processes being modeled, as well as a most likely cost output.

CAICAT Models

From the beginning, CAICAT has remained focused on providing a designer and design integrated product team (IPT) with the ability to rapidly assess the effects of their design decisions, using industry wide methods and practices. To do this the CAICAT team developed a suite of tools built on commercially available products. It consists of five modules: direct costs; indirect; factory simulation; research, development, test and engineering (RDT&E); and operations and support. During phase two of the CAI program each of these modules was developed, tested and prototype integration was completed. The current task is intended for completion of the integration of the above models in a CAD (CATIA and UNIGRAPHICS) environment so that the entire system can be maintained and commercialized in the future. The industry participants and the government each have a variety of legacy tools, processes and data that must be integrated by each member to be directly useful within each member's organization. The following is a list of CAICAT models, and descriptions of each:

RDT&E

The purpose of the CAICAT RDT&E model is to estimate the non-recurring engineering, test and tooling costs associated with a design based on part family, size, manufacturing process and test requirements.

Data was collected from each industry member and averaged by the Air Force. Cost estimating

relationships for non-recurring engineering, test, and tooling were then developed, reviewed and functionally validated.

Indirect Costs

The indirect model was developed by MCR Advanced Technology for the CAICAT team. It provides a mechanism to address non-touch labor and non-direct material costs which often account for over 70% of total cost. MCR developed a generic cost structure for each team member. This cost element structure can be modified to suit a company's specific needs.

Simulation Model

The objective of the Simulation model is to identify the resources required to produce a product for a given configuration and per a given schedule. The CAI team chose the Automod software from Auto Simulations Inc., to build the application required for CAICAT. The model outputs are stochastic so that it gives a realistic result in a production scenario. The output of the Simulation model can be used to feed the Indirect Cost Model (ICM), so that it is responsive to changes in capital equipment, floor space, cycle time, rate tooling, etc. Inputs such as manufacturing times, tooling and equipment requirements can be fed from SEER-DFM. The simulation model results can in turn be used as inputs to the indirect cost model.

Operation & Support Cost Model

The O&S model was developed by NAVAIR using F-18 data from Boeing, Northrop Grumman and internal Navy databases. The model developed is sensitive to material type, weight and function of the part being studied.

Long Term Vision

The Aerospace Industry will not cut chips without first having the designers, builders and users all having integrated their inputs digitally in a virtual environment. Just as we no longer rely on physical mockups, we will digitally replace DEM-VAL and EMD.

The task for the Cost Team will be to accept, interpret, and act upon the digital information (including design, mission profile, manufacturing processes, equipment, program parameters and all the performance "ilities"). These digital inputs will manipulate and drive the "Cost Engine". The job needs to be considered

as continually building knowledge of all the “Cost Intersections” until the entire process has been fully mapped. Identification or surfacing of the cost intersections is far more important than capturing the right dollar value for that cost (what is driving the cost). Corrections can be easily made. We can no longer afford to start from scratch every time a new program is started. Working together in Virtual reality to emulate design strategies and for the first time have real interaction between all the disciplines so that the most affordable design will become apparent. Push on the design in a 3-D space and watch it change, “real, instant feedback”. While the Virtual Design space may be limited to one room or factory it is far more likely to extend beyond any walls and encompass the entire industry from the smallest supplier to the end user. We change from having estimating skills that are reactive to the events that have occurred to the proactive analytical approach.

Conclusion

Above all, the CAI has been successful in changing history, paving the way for the airframe industrial base to work together. Their trail of success leaves behind a collaborative environment in which contractors, government agencies and model builders can share information. They’ve been successful in the development in a suite of commercially available software tools for the U.S. Industrial Base to use.

References

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